

MICRO PLASTICS

Plastic in Agricultural Production:
Impacts, Lifecycles and **LONG**-term Sustainability

THE MAGAZINE - November 2024

MICRO PLASTICS MACRO PROBLEMS

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TABLE OF

Editorial

**MICROPLASTICS:
THE ALARM BELL IS
RINGING** PAGE 4

**Last News
THEY ARE
EVERYWHERE!**
PAGE 5 & 15

**Contamination
AGRICULTURAL
SOILS IN DANGER**
PAGE 6

Interviewes

**“WE ARE ALREADY
IN THE RED ZONE”,
LUCA NIZZETTO**
PAGE 10

**“WE NEED TO
REDUCE POLLUTION,
KEEPING THE
AGRONOMIC
BENEFITS”**
PAGE 18

**International
THE UNITED
NATIONS MOBILISED**
PAGE 20

**UPDATE ON
BIODEGRADABLE
PLASTICS**
PAGE 24

**HIDDEN POLLUTION,
TANGIBLE EFFECTS**
PAGE 26

CONTENTS

Editorial

The subject of and concerns about microplastic pollution have made their way, starting from the oceans, to rivers, soils and now the human body. The extent of this pollution, caused by our oil-addicted societies, is still largely unknown, but it has entered the public debate, particularly following the scientific work of ocean expert Richard Thompson twenty years ago.

There are now warning signs about the extent of soil contamination, particularly in agricultural soils, which are crucial for our food. In the columns of this new magazine, we hear the warnings from Luca Nizzetto, researcher and leader of the PAPILLONS scientific consortium, funded by the European Horizon 2020 programme. Europe's agricultural soils are already in the red zone.

PAPILLONS, which is entering its home straight, sheds a harsh light on the extent of soil pollution, revealed by analyses in seven European countries. While there was every reason to believe that China — a pioneer in research into microplastics — was also the country most affected by this pollution, it seems that Europe is unfortunately not lagging behind.

There is therefore an urgent need to better understand microplastic contamination and the scale of its impact not only on the environment, but also on consumer health and the productivity of European farms. The addition of micro-plastics to the list of contaminants of the Soil Monitoring Law is one of the key steps needed.

But that is also the mission letter of this new magazine, 100% devoted to the subject of microplastics. Its aim is not only to accompany the end of the PAPILLONS consortium's work, but also to provide a tool to amplify the voice of scientists and the entire agricultural and food value chain, which must seize the subject to build the foundations of a microplastic-free food chain, including the private sector that can make the difference and scale up solutions.

Let's be clear: this is not about demonising agricultural plastics - they are a critical tool for our farmers, especially when the main sources of microplastic pollution seem to be a long way from the fields! On the other hand, we do need to take action to understand the sources, prevent the risks and find solutions to get the best out of plastics, but also from innovation, including in compostable plastics and other good practices, to pave the way for clean, healthy soils!

Luc Vernet, Editor
Secretary General of Farm Europe

Microplastics Newsflash

Nordic Countries' Joint Ministerial Declaration on Microplastics

Without concerted global action, annual microplastics release is set to double from 9 million tonnes (Mt) to 16 Mt in 2040.

As world leaders were gathered at the United Nation's General Assembly, Nordic countries' published a joint ministerial declaration calling for a legally binding Global Plastics Treaty that could cut microplastic pollution by 70% by 2040, according to their report.

INC fails to reach an agreement on Global Plastics Treaty

The fifth session of the International Negotiating Committee for a Global Plastics Treaty took place from November 25 to December 1 in Busan, South Korea. Despite growing concerns about the need to limit plastic pollution, UN negotiators were not able to reach an agreement on an international, legally binding treaty, the main controversy being the limitation of plastic production.

Plastic Overshoot Day

September 5th marked Plastic Overshoot Day, the point in the year when humanity's plastic waste surpasses the global capacity to manage it. As plastic production rises, waste management lags behind, leaving 69.5 million tonnes of plastic unhandled.

The upcoming UN Global Plastic Treaty aims to address this challenge by regulating plastic production and is key to protecting Europe's farmland from harmful microplastics, safeguarding food systems and ecosystems.

Traces of Microplastics in the Human Brain?

A new study published in September in JAMA Network Open detected the presence of microplastics in the human olfactory bulb, raising concerns about potential pathways for its entry into the brain.

These findings underline the urgency to tackle these pressing environmental and health issues related to global micro- and nano-plastic pollution. They come after previous research showing presence of microplastics in the human body.

Microplastics Contamination: Agricultural Soils in Danger

The use of agricultural plastics and the presence of plastics in soils are raising increasing concerns due to their potential effects on food security, health, and the environment, particularly regarding soil pollution by microplastics.

“Unfortunately, the main finding is that the microplastics contamination of EU soils is in line with data we have seen from previous studies in China, where there was a concern about high contamination,” says Luca Nizzetto, leading researcher of the 'PAPILLONS' project. He agreed to present the preliminary results of the project.

The overall aim of the project is to shed light on the sustainability of plastic use in European agriculture in terms of emissions of micro- and nanoplastics, the leakage of their chemical additives, and the impact of these on the soil.

Agricultural plastics, such as mulching films, tarpaulins, and nets, are widely used for various agricultural applications, including crop protection, water management, and soil conservation. However, over time, these plastics can degrade into small fragments called microplastics, typically less than 5 mm in diameter.

Soil pollution by microplastics in agriculture has two main causes: the spreading of agricultural sludge and the use of plastic mulch. Other sources include atmospheric deposition and the contamination of water used for irrigation.

Microplastics in Fertilizers and Irrigation

Where do microplastics come from? In a biological treatment plant, bacteria are in charge of depolluting the water. They 'eat' the organic matter and produce sludge. These bacteria do not degrade the fibers and fragments of plastic. These plastic particles can therefore aggregate with the sludge. Three-quarters of this sludge is then recycled for agricultural spreading and composting, explains Matthieu Combe, journalist and founder of Natura Sciences. In this way, microplastics and other contaminants find their way into agricultural soils

In Europe, a study by Ee Ling et al. estimates that 430,000 tonnes of microplastics enter farmland every year, solely as a result of sludge spreading. Water used for irrigation also contains microplastics that infiltrate the soil, but studies have yet to quantify this contribution.

Plastic pollutants originating from encapsulated fertilizers show the highest levels of plastic pollution in soil. Soil associated with greenhouse systems ranks second highest. Soils exposed to mulching film use generally have lower plastic levels. Only a very small number of studies define the precise size range of plastic particles detected.

Effects on Food Security

The presence of microplastics in agricultural soils raises concerns about their effects on food security. Microplastics can be ingested by plants and crops, potentially leading to contamination of food intended for human and animal consumption. Studies have shown that microplastics can persist in plant tissues and be transferred along the food chain. Moreover, soil pollution by microplastics can have consequences for human health and the environment. Research suggests that exposure to

microplastics can have adverse health effects, such as inflammation and hormonal disruptions, and can affect soil organisms, disrupt biological processes, and reduce biodiversity.

To assess the risks associated with soil pollution by microplastics from agricultural plastics, comprehensive studies are needed to understand their quantities in agricultural soils, sources, and their potential effects on food security, human health, and the environment.

Most plastics are buried or incinerated, with a significant amount ending up in nature, and few are recycled.

There is a need to find innovative solutions to capture these microplastics and to change the regulations to encourage local authorities to invest in modernizing their wastewater treatment plants.

Measures to reduce the use of agricultural plastics, encourage recycling and proper disposal of these materials, and promote sustainable alternatives can help mitigate the risks associated with soil pollution. Combating plastic pollution requires banning single-use plastics, reducing production, regulating the mismanagement of post-consumer plastics, and implementing circular economy principles.

European Legislation

One thing is certain: there isn't, for the moment, an established European Union policy regarding the presence of plastics in agricultural soils.

Nevertheless, the European Commission is actively working to reduce plastic pollution in many policy areas. The Soil Monitoring Law proposal, still in negotiation between the Council and the European Parliament, provides a generic EU framework for the monitoring, assessment, and management of soil health.

Member States would need to monitor the concentration of a national selection of organic contaminants in the soil and provide reasonable assurance that there is no unacceptable risk to human health or the environment. Member States would also need to define sustainable soil management practices that should be gradually implemented on all managed soils. These practices should be based on principles such as avoiding inputs or releases of substances into the soil that may harm human health or the environment or degrade soil health. The EU Soil Strategy refers to several actions to prevent plastic contamination, such as the REACH restriction on intentionally used microplastics, the communication on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics, and the Fertiliser Products Regulation, which establishes biodegradability criteria for plastic coatings in fertilizers and for agricultural plastic mulch films. The presence of microplastics in sewage sludge that is applied to agricultural soils was also a point of consideration in the evaluation of the Sewage Sludge Directive. In addition, a study was conducted for DG ENVI in 2021 on these plastics, including biodegradable ones.

By LIONEL CHANGEUR

PLASTIC POLLUTION IN FARM

“We don't have evidence that European soils are much better than in China” explains Luca Nizzetto, Senior Research Scientist at the Norwegian institute for Water Research - **interview by Lionel CHANGEUR & Luc VERNET**

Luca, what led you to focus on microplastics as a research topic?

Plastic pollution has been a hot topic in the past years with regard to the marine environment. In 2014, the Environmental Agency of Norway commissioned a report to evaluate the sources of microplastics entering the marine environment. We realized that land-based sources often end up in wastewater treatment plants and are mostly retained in sewage sludge, which is often used as a soil amending agent in agriculture. This process results in the transfer of hundreds of thousands of tonnes of plastics in Europe to farm soils.

I guess Papillons is the first study of this scale in Europe?

It is one of the first and earliest projects focusing on agricultural plastic in Europe. China, where the use of mulching films has resulted in visible pollution in soil, was a pioneer in studying plastic pollution in soils studies.

What are the main findings of your studies on the contamination of agricultural lands by plastics and microplastics?

We have now finalized the analysis of a broad survey that involved over 70 soils across Europe, covering seven countries. These soils include fields that have been treated with mulching film, soils treated with other types of agricultural practices (eg. fertilizers with sewage sludge or compost), and a non-treated control group. Unfortunately, the main finding is that the microplastics contamination of soils in Europe is in line with data we have

seen from previous studies in China.

We don't have clear evidence that European agricultural soils are better than those in other parts of the world. The main residues found originate from mulching films debris, compost and sewage sludge application. The estimated amount seems to be in the order of 100mg to 1g of plastics per kg of soil (0.01 to 0.1% in mass). Fields that experienced mismanagement of mulching films show record contamination levels.

Moreover, some control soils have been proven to be heavily contaminated as well, possibly through atmospheric fallout (eg. proximity to industrial sites). It is therefore important to underline that agricultural practices can be part of the problem, but they are not the only source.

Beyond agricultural practices, what are other main sources of this contamination?

One of the biggest, sources is the erosion of car tires. On average, at the end of its life cycle, each tire has lost at least 1 kg of weight. This releases micro and nanoplastics that end up in rivers or are eroded by wind and deposited on agricultural soil. If the road runoff is collected by a sewer (as it often happens in urban areas), the microplastics are also transferred to the sludge. Other sources are polymeric paints, which degrade due to solar radiation and temperature variations, and industrial activities where plastic is processed.

“Microplastics contamination of soils in Europe is in line with data that we have seen from previous studies in China”

LAND: A CRISIS UNCOVERED

What role do agricultural plastics play as potential sources of soil pollution? How does this impact plants and soils?

It's difficult to answer. I'm sure most farmers do their best to keep their fields as clean as possible. However, agricultural plastic remains an important pollution source. Mulching films are extremely challenging because even when the correct practices are put in place, the films break during recovery generating fragments. Among other agricultural sources, we find not only the encapsulation of seeds and fertilizers, but also pesticides and biodegradable plastics that can persist over a long time in certain conditions.

What measures could farmers take to prevent soil pollution? Are Biodegradable Plastics a solution?

This point is crucial: we should remember that plastic pollution in soil is poorly reversible, thus prevention is the key. At the moment it is fundamental to avoid bad management practices, such as burying mulching film, leaving it on site, or even burning it. Farmers using biodegradable materials should choose certified and properly labelled products, although currently there is concern about poor degradability in cold and arid climate. While it is true that farmers play a crucial role in reducing plastic pollution through proper resource management, they should not be left alone, and they should not be the only ones bearing the cost of better practices: we need the entire agricultural plastic value chain to be mobilized.

In some areas, there have been good developments in post-use management of waste. A.D.I.VALOR in France is an example of a best practice system that helps farmers dispose of the waste and deliver it to someone who can manage it properly. Unfortunately not all of this waste can, at the moment, be recycled. Product developers, industry, distributors, advisors, and waste managers should help by:

- Designing predictive models to minimize the chance of transfer and accumulation of plastic residues in soils,
- Establishing tools such as advisory services and guidelines for the application and retrieval of plastic polluting products, and creating best practices manuals on waste handling that should be available for farmers. In this context, clear information on the life-cycle of products should be given, to avoid using degraded products and release more plastics into soils.
- Innovating. Industries can help farmers by providing better, circular and reusable products.
- Setting up a clear traceability System and solid Labelling, including information on the correct use and the adequate equipment for safe operations. Practices resulting in the direct release of plastic to soil, such as leaving plant tags and clips in the field, should be dismissed.
- Regarding the second question, biodegradable plastics still release plastic debris to soil, and they may degrade more or less rapidly depending on the environmental conditions and the product itself.
- Another aspect to consider is that biodegradable plastics also contain additives. These chemicals are released during the degradation process. We do not have a sufficient understanding of the risk posed by these chemicals to the soil ecosystem, crop quality, and safety.

We should make a bigger effort to develop scientific understanding in this area, and new knowledge should be integrated to standards and regulation to ensure that only safe and truly degradable materials are used. The scientific community is calling for more robust risk assessments, better standards and quality control to ensure safe and sustainable use checks.

Do you think that the European legislation has gaps in this regard?

Yes. In the first draft of the Soil Monitoring Law, the European Commission did not even mention plastic. Thanks to the efforts made by the Papillons project, the European Parliament seems to be determined to address the issue. Plastic is the most conspicuous (in terms of abundance) contaminant of soils, showing a strong potential for affecting this ecosystem and its fertility.

The original, full interview
of Luca Nizzetto is
available on the Research
Consortium website,
Papillons-Horizon 2020

*“Farmers should
not be the only ones
bearing the cost for better
practices : we need the
entire agricultural plastic
value chain to be
mobilized”*

SAVE THE DATE
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2025
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INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND POLICY FORUM ON
PLASTIC IN THE AGRIFOOD CHAIN

MICROPLASTICS: THE SCALE OF THE CHALLENGE FOR THE AGRI-FOOD CHAIN

AGRIFOODPLAST is an independent research initiative uniting global experts, businesses, farmers and decision-makers working at the crossroads of plastics and food.

Plastic plays a vital role in food systems, but its use in agriculture, aquaculture, and fisheries can result in pollution and potential risks for biota and humans. This event is an opportunity to discuss the latest research on environmental and human risks of nano- and microplastics, and plastic-associated chemicals in food production and packaging, take part in a multi-actor forum of scientists, practitioners, and policy makers; share your vision on safer and more sustainable practices, and debate on needed policy developments and implementation measures.

The opening session on April 8 will provide a unique opportunity to learn about the outcome of the PAPILLONS' Horizon 2020 project, the first pan-European project of its scale related to plastics in agriculture, impacts, lifecycles & long-term sustainability.

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Latest Science News

THE IMPACT OF MICROPLASTICS ON EARTHWORMS AND SOIL HEALTH: A NETWORK OF COMPLEX INTERACTIONS

By Forsell, V., Saartama, V., Turja, R., Haimi, J., & Selonen, S.

Plastic contamination in agricultural soils is a growing concern, calling for a very careful management of plastic mulching films to avoid microplastics pollution. The latest study by Forsell et al. investigates the impact of microplastics from conventional polyethylene (PE) and biodegradable PBAT mulching films on the earthworms *Eisenia andrei*, which significantly contribute to soil-based ecosystem services, and are often termed as 'ecosystem engineers'.

Results of the study reveal that both types of microplastics affect earthworm health and soil properties, but in distinct ways. First, in terms of growth, PE microplastics led to a decrease in earthworm biomass at higher concentrations, while PBAT microplastics promoted growth at lower concentrations. Second, both PE and PBAT microplastics triggered significant oxidative stress responses, with specific

biomarkers (CAT, GR for PE; SOD, LPO for PBAT) being particularly affected.

Finally, concerning microplastics impact on soil, at higher concentrations, both types increased soil pH and water-holding capacity, potentially altering soil chemistry and contributing to the observed effects on earthworms.

These findings underscore the complexity of microplastics interactions in soil ecosystems, highlighting the need for ongoing research to fully understand the ecological risks posed by microplastic pollution.

NEW STUDY SHEDS LIGHT ON PLASTIC ADDITIVE CONTAMINATION IN AGRICULTURAL SOILS

By Dvorakova, D., Tsagkaris, A. S., & Pulkrabova, J.

Plastic films contain chemical additives that improve their durability but can degrade to microplastics and leach into the soil, potentially causing environmental harm. New research by the University of Chemistry and Technology in Prague develops a novel analytical approach to detect and quantify plastic additives (PAs) derived from agricultural

plastics, particularly mulching films, in soil using ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS).

The study uses three innovative extraction methods(*) to isolate and detect 16 plastic additives in soils, with recovery rates of up to 120%. Lab contamination from plastic consumables posed challenges to the monitoring of plastic additives, the use of glass apparatus and materials for plastic additive analysis is therefore strongly recommended. Finally, additives like bis (2-ethylhexyl) azelate and irganox 1010 were detected with precision, showing how these chemicals may accumulate in agricultural soils over time.

The findings highlight the need for further research into the ecotoxicological effects of plastic additives in soils. The methodology used paves the way for better monitoring and management of plastic pollution in agricultural contexts.

(*) Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) using hexane for non-polar additives, UAE with an aqueous methanol solution for polar additives, and a binary extraction method combining Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged, and Safe (QuEChERS) principles and UAE.

THE INVISIBLE THREAT TO SOILS: MICROPLASTIC RISKS FROM MISMANAGED AGRICULTURAL PLASTICS

By Briassoulis, D.

Recent study by the Agricultural University of Athens examines how the increasing use of agricultural plastics (AP) could lead to the contamination of soils by microplastics (MP) and nanoplastics (NP). These particles, especially from mulching films, irrigation systems, and protective covers, pose a risk of contaminating our soils and potentially

harming the environment, agricultural systems, and food security.

The results show that most APs are used for only a single season and often degrade into MPs/NPs due to exposure to environmental factors, releasing particles into the soil. Moreover, MPs are generated both directly from the breakdown of APs and indirectly from other sources, such as compost, fertilizers, and wastewater. This contamination can persist in soil layers and contribute to long-term pollution.

Products like mulching films and polymer-coated fertilizers pose the highest risk. Mismanagement of these products post-use increases the potential for pollution. In sum, soil pollution could impact soil health, crop quality, and even food safety. Biodegradable plastics and better end-of-life management of the materials can prevent these pollutants from accumulating. However, challenges remain in scaling up sustainable alternatives and improving recycling practices.

BIODEGRADABLE MULCHING FILMS: WHAT HAPPENS TO THEM AFTER 16 MONTHS IN AGRICULTURAL SOILS ?

By Convertino, F., Carroccio, S. C., Cocca, M. C., Dattilo, S., Dell'Acqua, A. C., Gargiulo, L., Nizzetto, L., Riccobene, P. M., Schettini, E., Vox, G., & Zannini, D.

A recent study published by the University of Bari has examined the fate of biodegradable mulch films (MFs) made of starch and PBAT (butylene-adipate-co-terephthalate) after being buried in agricultural soil for 16 months, in an experimental field in southern Italy.

Key findings highlight that both fresh and UV-aged biodegradable MFs do not completely degrade over time.

After 478 days, about 23 % and 17 % of the initial amount of BIO-0 and BIO-A192 (film materials) respectively were left in the soil. The starch in the films broke down faster, while the polyester part (PBAT) held on longer, leaving behind microplastic residues. While UV-aging actually accelerated starch degradation, the breakdown of PBAT was slower, leading to a stronger microplastic release to soil.

As a result, microplastics were leached into the soil, raising concerns about their long-term impact on soil health and the environment.

This research shows the complex nature of agricultural plastic films and demonstrates that climate and soil conditions play a major role in how these materials decompose, highlighting the importance of real-world field studies and the need for further investigation into the long-term impact of biodegradable MFs on our soils and ecosystems. With the growing use of biodegradable plastics in agriculture, it is crucial to understand how they really behave in different environments.

GIS MAPPING OF AGRICULTURAL PLASTIC WASTE IN SOUTHERN EUROPE

By Hachem, A., Convertino, F., Batista, T., Baptista, F., Briassoulis, D., Valera Martínez, D. L., Moreno Teruel, M. Á., Nizzetto, L., Papadaki, N.-G., Ruggiero, G., & Vox, G

New research into agricultural plastic waste (APW) in Southern Europe by the University of Bari sheds light on an escalating issue. A study involving GIS mapping has quantified and localized APW across four key countries—Italy, Spain, Greece, and Portugal—providing a critical foundation for sustainable management.

It was discovered that Spain, particularly Andalusia, generates the highest APW at 324,000 tons annually, while Portugal's Azores region has the lowest, with 428 tons. Furthermore, plastic waste from agricultural applications like nets, irrigation pipes, and covering films appears to be the largest contributor.

This pioneering work offers insights into plastic waste dynamics, helping policymakers identify hotspots and develop more effective waste management strategies.

The study's advanced methodology, integrating Plastic Waste Indices (PWI) with national agricultural census data, sets a precedent for future APW mapping across Europe.

The implications are clear: understanding and addressing APW is crucial for both environmental sustainability and the future of European agriculture. The data and insights derived from this research can guide policy decisions, inform infrastructure investments, and ultimately, shape a greener future.

Agricultural Plastics: Where Does the Sector Stand?

A discussion with Vincent Brack, Head of the French Committee for Plasticulture & Agro-environment (CPA) - Interview by Micol CATTANA.

Why did agricultural plastics become essential in modern farming practices? What specific benefits do they offer?

In the 1800s, Europe needed 1.6 hectares of agricultural land per person per year, but today, thanks to the modernization of agricultural practices, that number has dropped to 0.4 ha. Agricultural plastics have greatly contributed to this reduction by increasing yields and facilitating the mechanization of many tasks. They thus play a role in global food security. In horticulture, greenhouse films, tunnels, and mulching extend growing seasons, increase yields, and reduce losses by limiting weed growth, health risks, and the use of chemical inputs. Combined with efficient irrigation systems, they also enable water-efficient and climate-resilient agriculture. In livestock farming, plastics, in the form of twine, nets, and films, are crucial for preserving hay and fodder. Their use is compatible with practices such as organic, sustainable, and responsible farming, proving their relevance in modern, eco-friendly agriculture.

How can the economic importance of agricultural plastics be reconciled with growing environmental concerns, particularly regarding soil pollution from microplastics?

While it is clear that agricultural plastics will be an asset in facing climate

change and the agroecological transition, plasticulture sits at the intersection of two sensitive sectors: plastics and agriculture. First, it is important to note that agricultural plastics represent barely 4% of total plastic consumption in Europe. Additionally, although studies on agricultural soil pollution exist, they are often incomplete and fail to precisely identify the source of the microplastics (e.g. organic amendments, sewage sludge). Even though soil pollution from agricultural plastics is plausible, especially because of inadequate management, measures have been put in place to address this issue. It is crucial to ensure responsibility at every stage of the life-cycle of agricultural plastics. Poor end-of-life management would otherwise cancel out the environmental benefits. Collection and sorting are the first essential steps toward minimising the environmental impact of agricultural plastics.

How do you consider the evolution of national and international legislations (such as the United Nations International Treaty on Plastic Pollution) regarding microplastics in agricultural soils? What are the main challenges and opportunities for your sector?

When international legislations aim to reinforce the responsible use of agricultural plastics, they represent a positive evolution: adopting virtuous

practices is a common goal and offers opportunities for the agricultural sector to play an active role in developing international standards. The main challenge lies in finding a balance between reducing plastic pollution and maintaining the agronomic and economic benefits of agricultural plastics. The CPA (Comité de la Plastique et de l'Agroenvironnement) is actively involved in initiatives such as the FAO's Voluntary Code of Conduct (VCoC), which emphasises the importance of responsible and collective practices.

What solutions should be implemented to promote a more sustainable use of agricultural plastics and reduce microplastic pollution?

One key solution is to systematise the collection of used plastics while developing products that are more efficient (durable and waterproof) and thinner to reduce the amount of plastic used. Biodegradable plastic is also a promising alternative under certain conditions, as it decomposes in the soil thanks to microorganisms. In parallel, encouraging a circular economy through eco-modulation measures for products incorporating recycled materials and supporting research and development of recyclable plastics are essential steps to ensure a more sustainable use of plastics while preserving food sovereignty.

How do you work with farmers to raise awareness about microplastic-related issues and support them in adopting more sustainable practices?

In France, the EPR system directly involves farmers in the governance of agricultural plastic collection and recycling. The CPA also supports information and training campaigns, in partnership with ADIVALOR, to assist farmers in sorting and preparing plastics for collection. These initiatives enable optimal management of used plastics. The CPA collaborates with producer organisations, experimental stations, and research institutes to evaluate the

“The main challenge lies in finding a balance between reducing plastic pollution and maintaining the agronomic and economic benefits of agricultural plastics.”

agronomic, economic, and environmental impacts of solutions like biodegradable mulch films. Other innovative programs, such as RAFU (Recycling Used Agricultural Films), offer solutions to reduce the soiling rate of plastics, minimising their environmental impact (e.g., reducing unnecessary soil transport) and facilitating their recycling.

How do you imagine the future of the agricultural plastics sector in the upcoming years? What are the main challenges and opportunities that lie ahead?

One of the primary short-term objectives is to develop collection and recycling solutions for all products derived from plasticulture.

While collection is relatively simple thanks to a well-structured territorial network, ensuring local recycling of plastics requires significant investments, especially due to the soiling rate of used plastics. Producing high-quality recycled plastic pellets will be a key lever in establishing a circular economy. At the same time, it is necessary to increase knowledge about the environmental benefits of agricultural plastics while better measuring plastic losses into the environment. Another major challenge is decarbonizing the sector, with the goal of reducing CO2 emissions during plastic production and ensuring their recyclability. In the medium term, technological advances may allow the production of renewable plastics from bio-based materials derived from local biomass, paving the way for a more sustainable industry. The challenges are numerous, but they are within reach thanks to technological progress and collaboration among various stakeholders.

The UN Mobilises the Agri-Plastic Community to Overcome the Microplastics Challenge

FAO leads the way with a Voluntary Code of Conduct to promote sustainable plastic use in agriculture, supporting global efforts against microplastic pollution.

The use of agricultural plastics (APs) has been steadily increasing over the past few years, reaching approximately 10 million tonnes of plastic products (1) being utilised in farming every year. APs include mulching films, irrigation systems, protective covers and many other plastic products that help farmers enhance crop yield and quality, and make a more efficient use of water.

However, these benefits come against a set of environmental and health risks, especially as a consequence of the inadequate end-of-life management of these materials, due to the lack of access to proper waste management

infrastructure. When agricultural plastics degrade over time, breaking into smaller plastic fragments, the risk of micro- and nano-plastics contaminating the soil becomes a real concern.

For Lev Neretin and Giulia Carcasci from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), persistence and ecotoxicity constitute the major risks related to the presence of microplastics in soils. These materials can “remain in the soil for decades if not centuries, potentially disrupting soil functions and plant health and its ecosystem services,

(1) FAO. (2021). Assessment of agricultural plastics and their sustainability: A call for action. Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb7856en>

and thus jeopardising food security and nutrition. They can also transport toxic chemicals and pathogens, which pose a threat to food safety and human health". Moreover, according to the two experts, methodologies for measuring microplastics and methods for assessing exposure and risks are still in development. Therefore, a circular approach (Refuse, Redesign, Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, and Recover) applied to the use of agricultural plastics is urgently needed to reduce microplastic pollution in both terrestrial and aquatic environments.

Among the international initiatives that pursue this objective, FAO has been working on the development of a Voluntary Code of Conduct on the sustainable use and management of plastics in agriculture (VCoC), which will provide guidance for policy makers and practitioners to establish policy and management frameworks focused on a sustainable use of plastics in agriculture and promote "greener" alternatives and practices. This list of recommendations and good practices seeks to support the transformation of agrifood systems toward sustainability, including food security, safety, nutrition, human health, and environmental goals. The rising awareness of the risks deriving from plastic pollution prompted the United Nations to initiate negotiations for an international legally binding instrument to fight plastic pollution. The UNEA Resolution 5/14 (2), adopted on 2 March 2022, created an Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee (INC) with the objective of agreeing on a Treaty that would regulate the full life cycle of plastic, including its production, design, and disposal.

(2) United Nations Environment Assembly. (2022). Resolution adopted by the United Nations Environment Assembly on 2 March 2022: End plastic pollution: Towards an international legally binding instrument (UNEP/EA.5/Res.14). United Nations Environment Programme.

The resolution also expresses serious concern on the rising level of plastic pollution globally and officially recognizes microplastics to be part of the problem. Since then, five meetings of the INC have been held across the world, with the fifth and latest taking place from November 25 to December 1 in Busan, South Korea.

During these sessions, a growing consensus emerged among participants around the universal threat of plastic pollution to human health and the environment, and the need for urgent action. Despite general agreement, diverging views were brought up, particularly on whether the future treaty should focus on reducing plastic production or merely improving management, as well as on whether chemicals and polymers of concern should be subject to stringent regulations

Financial mechanisms and support dedicated to developing countries were also subject to contention. Hence, negotiators will have to address these issues during the upcoming meetings in 2025, since they did not manage to reach an agreement in Busan, contrary to what the roadmap set out by the UN had originally foreseen.

The adoption of an international legally binding instrument would be highly beneficial for the agricultural sector, notably by "fostering sector-specific approaches that reduce reliance on harmful plastic products and encourage the adoption of more sustainable alternatives and practices, by promoting circular economy practices and encouraging reuse, recycling, and better waste management of plastic products, by reducing plastic contamination of soils and water systems, and by facilitating the development of global standards and good practices for plastic use in agriculture", declare Carcasci and Neretin.

It also represents an opportunity to stimulate innovation in the agri-food sector.

In this context, FAO’s Voluntary Code of Conduct appears as an added value to the ongoing negotiations at the UN level. The Code wishes to be complementary to the international future framework by “assisting policymakers in developing and strengthening national strategies, policies and legal frameworks for the sustainable use and management of plastics in agriculture [...] and encouraging proactive measures by stakeholders, even before binding regulations are in place.”

The VCoC was presented for adoption by FAO Members at the 29th Session of the Committee on Agriculture (30 September – 4 October 2024). Now, all eyes will be turned to the next INC meetings, where the future Global Plastic Treaty is expected to take shape.

BY MICOL CATTANA
with contributions by Lev Neretin and Giulia Carcasci from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations

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INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND POLICY FORUM ON
PLASTIC IN THE AGRIFOOD CHAIN

MICROPLASTICS: THE SCALE OF THE CHALLENGE FOR THE AGRI-FOOD CHAIN

AGRIFOODPLAST is an independent research initiative uniting global experts, businesses, farmers and decision-makers working at the crossroads of plastics and food.

Plastic plays a vital role in food systems, but its use in agriculture, aquaculture, and fisheries can result in pollution and potential risks for biota and humans. This event is an opportunity to discuss the latest research on environmental and human risks of nano- and microplastics, and plastic-associated chemicals in food production and packaging, take part in a multi-actor forum of scientists, practitioners, and policy makers; share your vision on safer and more sustainable practices, and debate on needed policy developments and implementation measures.

The opening session on April 8 will provide a unique opportunity to learn about the outcome of the PAPILLONS' Horizon 2020 project, the first pan-European project of its scale related to plastics in agriculture, impacts, lifecycles & long-term sustainability.

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Biodegradable Plastics: a Science-Based Framework Needed

The use of biodegradable plastics in agriculture is becoming more and more frequent — for example, in the production of mulching films — leading the scientific community to explore the sustainability of such materials.

These agricultural films offer similar benefits to those made from conventional plastics in terms of crop performance and reliability; in this case, however, after use, they are left to degrade in the soil, thus avoiding the issue of their removal and disposal as waste.

PAPILLONS researchers' position, coinciding with that of a large portion of the international research community regarding bioplastics for agricultural use, affirms that these products' use should be governed by a science-informed risk analysis and management approach, rather than on a simple risk reduction approach. A recommendation document provided to the European Commission, available on the official PAPILLONS

website outlines this position in detail.

Research conducted by PAPILLONS and other international research groups shows that during the degradation of bioplastic films in soil, microplastics are formed. These micro-bio-plastics, similar to those derived from conventional plastics, can influence the chemical and physical properties of soils and affect plant growth and health at environmentally plausible concentrations.

Unlike microplastics from non-biodegradable plastics, which can persist indefinitely, micro-bio-plastics tend to degrade thanks to the activity of the soil's microbiological community. The duration of this process can vary from a few to many years, depending on environmental conditions, with cold temperatures or arid conditions expected to significantly delay the process. The continuous application of bioplastic films could lead to a transitory accumulation of micro-bio-

plastics in soil that could theoretically reach levels several-fold higher than the amount of material applied in a single application, possibly exceeding some thresholds for adverse effects.

While the option of removing bioplastic mulch films after use and transporting them to composting facilities to prevent the release of plastic debris might be a solution, PAPILLONS researchers have highlighted that the implementation of this option faces several challenges. It would entail various economic and environmental costs, such as those associated with waste transportation and processing. It would also require thicker films to enable collection without breaking and fragmenting, which would still result in the release of plastic debris. Thicker films would demand greater consumption of raw materials, impacting both the economic performance and the environmental footprint of these materials, and potentially leading to longer degradation times in composting facilities.

Other solutions proposed by PAPILLONS researchers include focusing on site- and material-specific risk assessments that consider both the physical and chemical interactions of micro-bio-plastics with soil and its biota. Such analyses should particularly assess the reversibility of these effects and the time required for the soil to recover its natural structure, function, and biodiversity. Under such a risk assessment framework focused fundamentally on the maintenance of soil resilience, management options could consider the possibility of temporarily and regularly suspending the use of these materials (e.g. through the rotation of agricultural practices and crops) on a given soil to allow for recovery. This would also require a quality control and labeling system to ensure the use of safe materials and the proper implementation of risk management measures. A similar regulatory framework exists in Europe, as

part of the food safety law, which should serve as an inspiration also for the bioplastic sector.

A third way suggested by PAPILLONS researchers highlights the vast potential for innovation in the bioplastics sector, which could provide new materials, ideally sourced from renewable resources, with better environmental compatibility. Leveraging a broader portfolio of innovative materials, new designs for mulching applications could enable degradation times better suited to the various environmental conditions in which they are used, reducing the progressive accumulation of micro-bioplastics over the medium and long term.

The PAPILLONS consortium essentially asserts that the use of bioplastics in agriculture should be guided by a risk analysis and management approach based on scientific evidence, supported by a new European regulatory framework that includes effective quality control and continuous updates to risk definition and analysis. Such a regulatory framework is still lacking globally, despite the growing use of bioplastics worldwide. PAPILLONS continues to work on providing new data and knowledge in this field, inspiring innovation in regulations, the agricultural sector, and industry toward eco-sustainable agriculture.

BY LUCA NIZZETTO

(*) PAPILLONS, 2022. Early policy recommendations from Papillons and Minagris.

Unseen Pollution, Tangible Effects: Microplastics' Impact on Plant Growth and Agricultural Sustainability

Plastic pollution in soils is likely to affect plant growth, crop quality and quantity, and the uptake of toxic substances from the soil. These effects have been observed even at environmentally plausible concentrations. A systematic review revealed that 114 relevant scientific studies have been published in international peer-reviewed journals addressing this issue since 2016. Review articles (representing 32% of the total number of retrieved publications) were excluded from this count.

As observed in the literature on soil effects, 80% of the experimental studies were published during or after 2022. Nearly all reviewed studies show that exposure to plastic debris in various forms (nano-, micro-, or macroplastics) affects one or more aspects of plant growth and quality. Only two studies, conducted at low exposure levels under field conditions, reported non-significant effects from either conventional or biodegradable plastics.

However, four other field-scale experiments involving the addition of microplastics made from conventional polyolefins to real agricultural soils reported adverse effects on plant growth, crop yield, and quality, even at levels as low as 0.01% plastic in the soil. Two additional field-scale experiments demonstrated that large debris from both conventional and biodegradable plastic films can affect the distribution and growth of non-agricultural plants on sandy littoral soils. Regardless of the exposure levels in the different studies, about 90% of the experiments showed significant effects on plant growth or quality at the lowest tested concentrations. This indicates that the current body of evidence is insufficient to determine a safety threshold that would protect plants from plastic pollution in soils. Nevertheless, a tentative threshold can be estimated to lie below 0.05%, regardless of the characteristics and composition of the plastic pollution.

Looking more closely at studies conducted under more realistic exposure scenarios -field, mesocosms, or pot experiments, with plausible plastic concentrations lower than 0.1%- reveals a broad range of plant responses to plastic-contaminated soils. These include:

1. **Growth Inhibition:** While inhibitory effects on individual plant growth or crop yield were prevalent, some studies suggested that microplastics at low concentrations might promote growth in certain parts of plants. These findings highlight changes in the soil habitat induced by plastic debris.

2. **Physiological Stress Responses:** Plants exhibited defensive responses to plastic pollution in the soil through changes in antioxidant enzyme activity.

3. **Altered Rhizosphere Microbial Community Structure and Activity:** Both biodegradable and non-biodegradable microplastics can alter the structure and diversity of soil microbial communities, including arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF), which play a critical role in plant health and nutrient uptake.

4. **Nutrient Uptake:** Different types of plastic mulch residues were observed to significantly affect the total nitrogen and magnesium uptake by plants, potentially impacting plant nutrition and health. These effects could be mediated by plastic-induced changes in the soil.

5. **Soil-Plant Contamination Dynamics:** The presence of microplastics can enhance the bioavailability and mobility of heavy metals in the soil, influencing their absorption and accumulation in plants.

Based on this evidence, the growing plastic contamination in agricultural soils should be considered a concern for both food safety and security.

BY **LIONEL CHANGEUR**

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